

USE OF POST-CORE ABUTMENTS MADE OF ZIRCONIUM DIOXIDE

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The article presents results on the determination of the strength properties of individual post-core abutments made of zirconium dioxide in different areas of the dental arch under varying occlusal load angles. The highest strength was observed in molars under a 0° load angle, while the lowest strength was recorded in incisors under a 30° load angle.

Keywords: post-core abutment; zirconium dioxide; strength

Introduction

Restoring the coronal portion of a tooth after endodontic treatment and using tooth roots for prosthetic reconstruction remains a pressing issue in modern dentistry. However, many practical questions remain unresolved. The main goal in restoring teeth with a damaged coronal structure is to ensure adequate retention of the final restoration while maximizing protection of the tooth root from fracture. A widely accepted solution to this problem is the use of various types of posts and post-core systems [1–4].

The diversity of clinical situations in restoring teeth with compromised coronal structure has led to a wide range of sizes, shapes, fabrication methods, physical and mechanical properties of dental posts and post-core restorations, as well as their interactions with the tooth's hard tissues. It is well known that teeth after endodontic treatment are more brittle, and the likelihood of their long-term preservation in the dental arch is lower. According to statistics, fractures of endodontically treated teeth occur significantly more often. Numerous studies have shown that most failures in restoring endodontically treated teeth are related to biomechanical or technological factors rather than biological ones.

The choice of material for post fabrication is of critical importance, as it must possess a combination of properties, including mechanical resistance to functional loads, biocompatibility, corrosion resistance, and the ability to maintain the aesthetics of the remaining tooth structure, gingiva, and future restorations. Historically, metal posts were most widely used due to their mechanical properties. In addition to high strength, metal posts provide excellent radiopacity and are relatively inexpensive. However, the oral cavity is an aggressive environment for metals, and the potential pathological effects of metal alloys on the human

body—including chemical toxicity, galvanic effects, and allergic reactions—are well documented.

Recently, there has been increasing development and application of non-metallic materials. Standard posts made of zirconium dioxide, partially stabilized with 4–5% yttrium oxide, have appeared on the dental market. This material offers not only good biocompatibility and excellent aesthetics, similar to glass-ceramics, but also radiopacity and high mechanical resistance, unlike glass-ceramics. Today, a wide range of prosthetic structures can be fabricated from zirconium dioxide, including inlays, crowns, bridges of any length, implant-supported prostheses, and post-core systems.

The use of standard post systems is not always appropriate, especially in cases of severe tooth destruction, where individually fabricated posts are recommended. Other limitations of standard post systems include inadequate adaptation of the intracanal portion to the root canal shape, limited guarantee of reconstruction stability, insufficient radiopacity, and multi-layered, multi-component design. An alternative approach is the fabrication of individualized zirconium dioxide post-core restorations.

Objective of the study: To determine the strength properties of individual zirconium dioxide post-core abutments in different regions of the dental arch under varying occlusal load angles.

Materials and Methods

Testing was performed using a universal testing machine INSTRON 5900 (USA). Extracted natural teeth (incisors, premolars, and molars) were used in the study. A special cylindrical fixture was developed for the universal testing machine INSTRON.

The extracted teeth were prepared: root canals were shaped for the fabrication of post-core restorations while maintaining approximately 2 mm of tooth hard tissue and forming a supragingival collar. The

teeth were scanned in a dental laboratory using a ZhirkonZahn S600 ARTI scanner (Germany), modeled in the ZhirkonZahn software, and the post-core abutments were milled using a ZhirkonZahn M5 milling unit (Germany). The fabricated abutments were cemented into the teeth using glass ionomer cement Fuji I (GC, Japan).

Next, the teeth were scanned again for crown fabrication. Crowns were modeled in the same software and milled from Ice Zircon Translucent zirconium dioxide. Crowns were cemented using Fuji I glass ionomer cement. The samples were then placed in cylindrical molds filled with bone cement Heraeus (Palacos MV, Germany), chosen for its mechanical properties closely matching those of natural bone.

The cemented samples were subjected to single-cycle destructive loading at angles of 0°, 15°, and 30°. Results were recorded in tables and statistically processed using SPSS 12.0.2 for Windows.

Results

Analysis of the results showed: **Incisors:** 0° load: 256.2 ± 15.11 MPa, 15° load: 214.84 ± 14.71 MPa, 30° load: 86.27 ± 8.93 MPa. **Premolars:** 0° load: 327.43 ± 22.65 MPa, 15° load: 298.26 ± 16.68 MPa. **Molars:** 0° load: 487.95 ± 44.16 MPa, 15° load: 463.48 ± 48.94 MPa.

The study demonstrated that increasing the load angle significantly affected the strength of the tested samples. Molars under a 0° load exhibited the highest strength, while incisors under a 30° load showed the lowest.

When considering the use of zirconium dioxide post-core restorations in the oral cavity, individual occlusal characteristics of the patient must be taken into account. Based on literature data reporting the average inclination angle of maxillary incisors in an orthognathic bite (~30°) and masticatory forces in the anterior

region (196.1–294.2 MPa), the use of zirconium dioxide post-core restorations in this region may not be justified. As the load angle increases, the strength of the posts decreases, raising the risk of treatment complications such as post fracture.

The experiment is ongoing, with the goal of establishing precise parameters for tooth preparation and fabrication of post-core restorations, considering the physical and mechanical properties of the material and oral conditions.

Conclusion

Bench testing of teeth from different functional groups with zirconium dioxide post-core restorations demonstrated higher strength in posterior teeth compared to anterior teeth. This highlights the need for further optimization of post dimensions and preparation limits for the roots of teeth from different functional groups.

References

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